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Understanding channel choice in users' reporting behavior: Evidence from a smart mobility case

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ABSTRACT

Public service producers are heavily investing in the development and implementation of more efficient new digital channels to engage users in citizen sourcing efforts, such as the reporting of public service-related issues. Nevertheless, user-reporters have continued to favor earlier implemented channels including traditional (e.g., phone, office) and e-government channels (e.g., web, email) over new digital channels such as m-government channels (e.g., mobile applications). Drawing on channel choice literature and theories, this study aims at explaining users' reporting behavior by examining the role of users' personal factors, including digital divide determinants, users' service experience, and channel satisfaction. We use a combination of survey and log data on actual reporting behavior among smart bike-sharing users to explain users' channel choice. Using a multinomial logistic regression, we found that the digital divide predicts user-reporters' channel choice. Moreover, user-reporters with a longer service membership favor traditional and e-government channels, over the newly implemented m-government channels. Finally, user-reporters' satisfaction with the mobile application is negatively associated with the user-reporters' choice of traditional and e-government channels. Our results expand and update the empirical evidence on channel choice at the user level, and provide insights for public service producers who aim at enhancing public service delivery through digital users' engagement.

1. Introduction

Over the last decades, citizens have been gaining a more active role in the functioning of their government, shifting from mere clients or customers to contributors, co-producers or active knowledge producers (Cardullo & Kitchin, 2018; Linders, 2012). The concept of citizen reporting, also known as citizen sourcing in the monitoring phase, has flourished in the context of what Linders (2012) frames as the shift from e-government to 'we-government'. Citizens act as user-reporters when they voluntarily report service-related issues (such as non-urgent problems or incidents they witnessed) to the regular (public or private) producers of public services, identifying opportunities for improvement. This phenomenon has its roots in the traditional 311 hotline (115 in some European cities), a non-emergency alternative to the 911 call centers in U.S. cities. Via 311 calls, user-reporters interact with the government by providing data on different aspects of the city and its services (Kopackova & Libalova, 2019; Linders, 2012; Offenhuber, 2015).

Later, thanks to technological advances and the rapid diffusion of

internet access and use, (new) digital channels were made available for citizen reporting at the city level (Abu-Tayeh, Neumann, & Stuermer, 2018; Schmidhuber, Hilgers, Gegenhuber, & Etzelstorfer, 2017a; Thijssen & Van Dooren, 2016). For instance, the phone-only 311 systems have been expanded to introduce internet-based service reports via websites, emails, social media sites, and mobile applications (Clark & Brudney, 2019). These advances can also be illustrated by the widely-studied platforms *FixMyStreet* (UK) and *SeeClickFix* (US) that allow users to digitally report non-emergency issues on different services offered by the city including downed street lights or road surface defects.

The implementation of new digital channels, such as mobile applications, can nurture the collaboration between producers of public services and user-reporters, while reshaping users' reporting behavior (Clark & Brudney, 2019; Fugini & Teimourikia, 2016; Lember, Brandesen, & Tonurist, 2019; Linders, 2012). For instance, the bike-sharing system *Mobike* in China has included reporting options in their mobile applications allowing the local government and producers to respond quickly and effectively to service issues such as broken bikes or vandalism (Lan et al., 2017). Prior to the rise of mobile applications,

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citizens could report issues by filling out a web-based form or by sending an email. However, the implementation of mobile reporting applications allowed public service users to provide more detailed and in-situ information, such as the location and urgency of the issue (Clark & Brudney, 2019; Ertiö, Ruoppila, & Thiel, 2016).

Expectations are high concerning the implementation of new digital channels since they are claimed to increase inclusion (Michels, 2011), equity (Gil-Garcia, Zhang, & Puron-Cid, 2016) and efficiency (Reddick, 2017). Linders (2012) and O'Reilly (2010) also point out that they can empower people, foster local activism, unleash social innovation, and reinvigorate democracy. In light of these expectations, public service producers are heavily investing in developing and implementing new digital channels to engage citizens as contributors and gather real-time feedback (W-N. Wu, 2017). However, user-reporters still massively rely on traditional channels, such as the phone or visiting the public service front office, compared to newly implemented digital channels (Madsen & Hofmann, 2019; Madsen & Kræmmergaard, 2015).

Although many factors have been explored to explain users' preferences for traditional over (new) digital channels, the evidence remains mostly inconclusive. Furthermore, most of the existing channel choice literature examines users' behavioral intention to report through the channels, and focuses especially on traditional and e-government channels (Madsen & Kræmmergaard, 2015). Building on these observations, our study aims to extend the empirical evidence on user-reporters' channel choice of traditional, e-government and m-government channels in a real-life setting by examining how user-reporters' personal factors, including user-reporters' personal characteristics and experiences, relate to their actual channel choice. To answer this research question, our study simultaneously examines the potential uneven access and use of ICT, known as 'the digital divide' (van Dijk, 2020), user-reporters' service experience (Rey-Moreno, Medina-Molina, & Barrera-Barrera, 2018; Teerling & Pieterse, 2011), and user-reporters' channel satisfaction (Montoya-Weiss, Voss, & Grewal, 2003; Reddick & Turner, 2012).

To address our research aim, we analyze data from user-reporters of a smart bike-sharing system ($n = 3530$) in Flanders (Belgium) through a multinomial logistic regression. Data were obtained from log data on users' actual reporting behavior combined with a survey among the smart bike-sharing user-reporters. We found that both user-reporters' personal characteristics and experiences are significantly related to user-reporters' choice of traditional and e-government channels over the newly implemented m-government channel.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the relevant literature on channel choice and users' personal factors as determinants of channel choice behavior. Section 3 develops the theoretical arguments and hypotheses. Section 4 elaborates on the research setting, data, and method in detail. Section 5 presents the empirical results. Section 6 discusses the research and managerial implications, limitations, and avenues for future research. Section 7 offers some concluding remarks.

2. Literature review

2.1. Channel choice

Channel choice theory aims at explaining the prevalent use of certain channels over others when users interact with public service producers. Channel choice is defined by Reddick, et al. (2020, p. 81-82) as "the selection of a channel by a citizen either for contact to address a particular service issue or as an ongoing preference or practice for government contact". The 'channels' are the different means through which citizens can get in contact with the government for information and services (Reddick et al., 2020).

Previous channel choice studies clustered the different channels as a continuum into three groups. First, *traditional* channels were

implemented before the development of e-government channels, and include channels such as office visits, phone calls, and postal mail. Second, *e-government* channels include, among others, emails, websites, text messages, and social media networks. These channels are considered more cost-efficient than the traditional channels (Ebbers, Pieterse, & Noordman, 2008; Pieterse & Ebbers, 2020; Reddick & Turner, 2012). Finally, *m-government* channels are new digital channels based on wireless and mobile technologies, such as mobile applications and SMS. M-government channels allow user-reporters to provide in-situ information, such as the location and urgency of the issue reported. The benefits are related to the so-called 'situated engagement' and ubiquity. This means that user-reporters can reflect on the issue on the place it was experienced, allowing richer descriptions (Ertiö, 2018; Reddick, 2017; Reddick et al., 2020; Serra, Carvalho, Ferreira, Vaz, & Freire, 2015).

Channel choice studies have mainly explained users' channel choice through task characteristics, e.g., task complexity and ambiguity (Ebbers, Jansen, Pieterse, & van de Wijngaert, 2016); channel characteristics, e.g., ease of use, usefulness (Pieterse, Teerling, & Ebbers, 2008); situational constraints, e.g., time availability (Wolf, Bick, & Kummer, 2017), and personal factors, e.g., socio-demographics, habits, and experiences (Ebbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014).

The factors influencing users' channel choice have been mainly informed by previous channel choice studies and imported theories. More particularly, channel choice scholarship has mostly relied on adoption studies, marketing theory, and theories from media studies such as Media Richness Theory (MRT) (Draft & Lengel, 1986) and Channel Expansion Theory (CET) (Carlson & Zmud, 1999). MRT assumes that media's (i.e., channels) characteristics (e.g., immediacy of feedback, personalization, contact speed) are fixed properties and that users choose the channel that is most suitable for the task at hand based on those properties (Pieterse et al., 2008). CET, on the other hand, aims to improve and expand this theory, and argues that the properties of channels are not fixed but rather constructed through users' experiences, that will in turn allow them to choose the channels for a broader range of tasks (Carlson & Zmud, 1999; Pieterse, 2009).

In their most recent study, Pieterse and Ebbers (2020) examine the influence of tasks and users' personal factors across different datasets from 2007 and 2018 on users' channels' preferences and use. Although they observed that users prefer to use e-government channels, in most cases, they found that users' shift from traditional to digital channels can mainly be explained by users' experience and characteristics. In line with CET, this finding indicates that channels are mostly chosen by users for all types of tasks and situations based on experience, while the relationship between tasks and channel choice is less straightforward. To sum up, in a context where users can choose among multiple channels, the most important differences on channel use might be explained through users' personal characteristics and experiences (Pieterse & Ebbers, 2020). In this study, we therefore aim to dive into this assumption by examining the role of users' personal factors on users' channel choice for a specific task: users' reporting behavior.

2.2. Users' personal factors as determinants of channel choice

Channel choice literature has differentiated users' personal factors into two dimensions that are associated with channel choice behavior (Kubicek, 2016; see also Madsen & Kræmmergaard, 2015). First, *subject-related personal factors* such as users' socio-economic status (Reddick, Abdelsalam, & Elkadi, 2012; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014; Schmidhuber, Hilgers, Gegenhuber, & Etzelstorfer, 2017b). Second, *channel-related personal factors* including users' channel and service experience and habits (Reddick, 2017; Rey-Moreno & Medina-Molina, 2017).

In the context of channel choice studies, users' socio-economic status, as determinant of channel choice, is traditionally examined through the lens of the digital divide (e.g., Ebbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014). The digital divide generally refers to the

gap between people who have access and use digital media to participate and engage in social, civil, and public activities, and those who do not (Norris, 2001; van Dijk, 2020). Although access and usage divides are argued to be narrowing in developed countries, new gaps in the way citizens use new technologies are widening. For instance, mobile applications (m-government channels) are increasingly implemented in the public sector to engage with public services' users due to their expected efficiency and mobility advantages. This new technology is claimed to engage more disadvantaged individuals and has become one of the prime means of users' reporting initiatives. However, previous research on mobile application use observed that the so-called 'usual suspects' - well-educated young men -, have more competences to engage in activities such as users' reporting through new technologies, while more disadvantaged users are more likely to use new technologies for entertainment (Ertiö et al., 2016).

Most channel choice scholars agree that disadvantaged users are less likely to use (new) digital channels, such as m-government channels. Yet, to date, mixed-results and contradictory findings have been observed (Pieterse & Ebbers, 2020). For instance, some scholars have found no significant relationship between gender and channel choice (Ebbers, Jansen, Pieterse, & van de Wijngaert, 2016; Ebbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Okunola, Rowley, & Johnson, 2017), while others observed that men are more likely than women to use (new) digital channels (Reddick et al., 2020; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014; van Dijk, 2020). Moreover, according to Reddick et al. (2012), being fully employed - indicating a higher socio-economic status - has a positive influence on digital channel choice. Still, scholars have reported different findings concerning the relationship between education level and channel choice. On the one hand, previous studies found that education is negatively associated with traditional channels choice, and positively associated with e-government channels (Ebbers, Jansen, Pieterse, & van de Wijngaert, 2016; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014) and m-government channels choice (Reddick et al., 2020). On the contrary, Ebbers, Jansen, and van Deursen (2016) observed that education level is not a significant predictor of channel choice.

Channel choice studies have also examined users' experiences as part of users' personal factors. First, users' experience with channels and services appears to be related to the development of habits that might inhibit the adoption of channel innovations. Teerling and Pieterse (2011) found evidence that user-reporters' habits are guided by previous experiences instead of rational assessments that are linked to user-reporters' channel choice. In the same line, Rey-Moreno et al. (2018, p. 13) observed that "the preference toward a channel is a choice based on previous experiences".

Second, satisfactory channel experiences, operationalized as satisfaction with (new) digital channels, might induce the adoption of the respective channel (Ebbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Reddick, 2017). Limayem, Hirt, and Cheung's (2007) work on the role of habits in the adoption of information systems demonstrated that satisfaction promotes the development of new habits that induce users' adoption of innovation. This evidence aligns with channel choice scholars who argued that channel satisfaction should be included as an explanatory factor when examining channel choice, since satisfaction with a channel could promote the use of the respective channel (Reddick et al., 2012). Accordingly, recent work on channel choice has observed the relevance of user-reporters' channel satisfaction to explain the choice of traditional and e-government channels (e.g., Ebbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Montoya-Weiss et al., 2003; Reddick, 2017).

Based on the review of the literature examining users' personal factors, our study mainly provides a three-fold contribution to the channel choice field. First, channel choice scholars have almost exclusively examined the choice and use of traditional and e-government channels, while the choice of m-government channels have received very limited attention (albeit the exceptions of Reddick, 2017, and Reddick et al., 2020 studies in China). Therefore, this article contributes to the channel choice theory by examining and comparing a wide array

of channels including an m-government channel. This contribution becomes even more relevant in light of the increasing government's adoption of m-government channels to interact with citizens, and the expected advantages of these channels, such as situated engagement and ubiquity (W-N. Wu, 2017).

Second, to the best of our knowledge, this study is the first of its kind to specifically examine the role of users' personal factors on channel choice in a real-life setting with a large sample of actual behavior data. The examination of channel choice using actual reporting behavior reduces potential common methods bias as well as social desirability bias, and consequently, increases the validity and reliability of the findings (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee, & Podsakoff, 2003). Yet, to date, most channel choice studies have exclusively relied on users' intention to use a channel (de Jong, Neulen, & Jansma, 2019; Ebbers, Jansen, Pieterse, & van de Wijngaert, 2016; Ebbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; W. J. Pieterse & Ebbers, 2020; Reddick et al., 2012; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014; Rey-Moreno et al., 2018; W-N. Wu, 2017). As recently claimed by Madsen and Hofmann (2019), p. 140–141, "[t]o move the CC field further forwards, scholars have repeatedly called for new empirical studies from actual use settings [...] many studies have been conducted in controlled and artificial settings, which may limit their explanatory power for actual use settings".

Third, based on our literature review, we observed that while channel choice studies highlight the relevance of users' personal factors, the findings are mostly inconsistent. Even more, most studies are neglecting the mechanisms explaining the process behind the association between users' personal factors and channel choice (Reddick et al., 2020; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014). It is therefore essential to advance channel choice theory by providing a more precise understanding of users' personal characteristics and experiences, beyond the usual descriptive level of reasoning. Our study therefore aims at further identifying these mechanisms in the following section.

3. Theoretical background and hypothesis development

Our study examines how user-reporters' personal factors, including user-reporters' personal characteristics and experiences, relate to their actual channel choice. Several theories can inform the understanding of users' personal factors' role in channel choice (Madsen & Kræmmergaard, 2015). In this study, therefore, we present a model based on three sets of hypotheses built on the summary of existing literature and theories reflecting both user-reporters' personal characteristics and experiences as channel choice determinants. First, we draw upon the digital divide theory and channel choice literature to understand the personal factors related to the user-reporters' categorical inequalities, including socio-demographics (i.e. age, gender, education level, and occupational status) and internet use (Ebbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014; van Dijk, 2020). Second, we build on channel choice literature, Status Quos Bias, Information Systems Continuance, and Channel Expansion theories to examine user-reporters' personal factors related to their experience with the service and channel satisfaction (Rey-Moreno et al., 2018; van Dijk, Peters, & Ebbers, 2008).

3.1. Users' personal characteristics

The first set of hypotheses seeks to explain user-reporters' channel choice through the digital divide. This theoretical concept states that users' channel choice is related to the differences in users' personal characteristics (Ebbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Madsen & Kræmmergaard, 2015). In order to explain the categorical inequalities between user-reporters' channel choice, we build on the relational approach (Wellman and Berkowitz, 1988). The relational approach focuses on the categorical differences between users' characteristics. The most important categorical inequalities determining the digital divide are educational and occupational position, age, gender and internet use. Yet, the differences should not be understood in an individualistic

manner, but as a result of the competition of categorical pairs. This approach allows an enhanced understanding of the mechanisms behind the digital divide determinants (van Dijk, 2013).

A first personal characteristic, gender, has traditionally been considered a relevant predictor when examining channel choice (Madson & Krammergaard, 2015). Digital divide studies argue that women are in a disadvantaged position compared to men concerning the use of (new) digital channels due to aspects related to education, tradition and culture, economic inequality, and ICT design. Because of these inequalities, men are often the first to adopt new technologies, excluding women in daily practice (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2019; van Dijk, 2020). Other studies argued that the digital gender gap, in a context of high internet access, may lead to differences in the pattern of use (Fatehikia, Kashyap, & Weber, 2018; van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014).

Another relevant digital divide predictor of channel choice is age. Channel choice scholars argue that younger users prefer to use m-government channels while older users are more likely to contact the government via traditional channels (Reddick et al., 2020). The mechanism behind this preference for traditional over e-government and m-government channels relates to the elderly's limited digital skills compared to younger users, and service's user-friendliness (Ebbbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016). Moreover, occupational status and education level also play a role in user-reporters' channel choice. It is expected that, due to the unequal distribution of resources, the digitally engaged user-reporters are more likely to be employed and highly educated. Finally, daily use of the internet is related to the development of the necessary skills to use digital channels. That means that users with high internet experience would have greater abilities and willingness to interact with the government via (new) digital channels compared to users with a low internet experience (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2019).

Based on the above theoretical observations, and the understanding of m-government channels as newly implemented digital channels, we formulate the following hypotheses¹:

H1a. Male user-reporters are more likely than female user-reporters to report via the m-government channel, compared to the e-government and traditional channels.

H1b. Younger user-reporters are more likely than older user-reporters to report via the m-government channel, compared to the e-government and traditional channels.

H1c. Professionally active user-reporters are more likely than professionally inactive user-reporters to report via the m-government channel, compared to the e-government and traditional channels.

H1d. Higher educated user-reporters are more likely than lower educated user-reporters to report via the m-government channel, compared to the e-government and traditional channels.

H1e. User-reporters who use the internet more frequently are more likely than user-reporters who use the internet less frequently to report via the m-government channel, compared to the e-government and traditional channels.

3.2. Users' personal experiences

The second set of hypotheses aims at explaining user-reporters' channel choice through their personal experiences, also known as channel- and service-related personal factors (Kubicek, 2016). The choice of a respective channel is linked to the experiences users have with the channels and the services at hand. Some experiences might have an inhibiting effect on channel choice. For instance, user-reporters' service experience promotes the development of habits and, thus,

¹ See section 4.3. and Appendix A. for more details on the operationalization of the variables.

preferences for channels that have been initially implemented by the public service producers compared to innovative channels (Rey-Moreno et al., 2018; Teerling & Pieterse, 2011). This means that users' choice of new digital channels might be inhibited by the habits of using earlier implemented channels. Other users' experiences might enable and induce the choice of certain channels. For instance, user-reporters' satisfaction with a new digital channel results in their choice for the respective channel (Montoya-Weiss et al., 2003; Reddick & Turner, 2012). This argument purports to explain user-reporters' choice of a newly implemented channel as conditional to having a satisfactory experience with that channel.

3.2.1. Users' service experience

The theory of the Status Quos Bias (SQB) states that there is a cognitive tendency to favor the current situation, inhibiting the perceptions toward the use of new technologies (i.e., channels). Therefore, users are more inclined to choose a channel they already use because preferences are linked with a "status quo bias" – an irrational preference to maintain the "current state" (Wang, Song, & Yang, 2013). As claimed by Rey-Moreno et al. (2018), users' channel preferences are influenced by their continued experience with that channel. Therefore, one could argue that long-term members and frequent users might consequently have a habit of using prior implemented channels over new channels. Building on these observations and existing channel choice studies (e.g., Rey-Moreno et al., 2018; Teerling & Pieterse, 2011), we consider experience with the service to be negatively associated with the choice of newer channels (i.e., m-government channels) compared to previously implemented channels (i.e., traditional and e-government channels). Hence, we formulate the following hypothesis:

H2. User-reporters who have more service experience are less likely than user-reporters with less service experience to report via the m-government channel, compared to the e-government and traditional channels.

3.2.2. Users' channel satisfaction

The influence of channel satisfaction as determinant of channel choice is widely acknowledged in channel choice theories, particularly in the media choice field and marketing (Carlson & Zmud, 1999; Ebbbers, Jansen, Pieterse, & van de Wijngaert, 2016). Accordingly, Thorngate (1976, p. 32) argues that "if a response generated in an interaction is judged to be satisfactory, it will tend to be reproduced under subsequent, equivalent circumstances". This is in line with theory on information systems continuance, which indicates that a satisfactory experience with certain behavior is a key factor for adopting a new system (Limayem et al., 2007). Therefore, channel satisfaction is expected to be positively associated with channel use preference (Devaraj, Fan, & Kohli, 2002). In light of these observations and previous channel choice studies (e.g., Ebbbers, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Reddick, 2017), we argue that user-reporters' satisfaction with the m-government channel is positively related to the choice of the m-government channel compared to the prior implemented traditional and e-government channels. This assumption leads to the following hypothesis:

H3. User-reporters who are more satisfied with the m-government channel are more likely than user-reporters who are less satisfied with the m-government channel to report via the m-government channel, compared to the e-government and traditional channels.

4. Data and method

4.1. Research setting

To test the hypotheses on the role of user-reporters' personal factors on their channel choice, we draw on user-reporters' actual reporting behavior data in one of the most successful dock-based smart bike-sharing services in Flanders (Belgium), hereafter referred to as

SmartBike. The *SmartBike* public service was launched in 2011 in a major city in Flanders, led by the city's Department of Urban Development. The primary producer is a private company that offers this service internationally, although *SmartBike* responds to both the city and the private partner (c.f. Rodríguez Müller & Steen, 2019). The service is part of the city's efforts to introduce smart solutions and innovations in different public services, specifically in mobility. It aims to offer an alternative mobility service that is available 24/7 and provides a solution to the so-called 'first/last mile problem'. Because of its accessibility and distribution of bike-stations in the city and surroundings, *SmartBike* is one of the most successful public smart bike-sharing systems in Belgium. The most recent figures from the city's open data platform indicates that more than 80% of its inhabitants can reach a bike-station in 5 min or less by foot.

SmartBike's users can voluntarily report service-related issues about the functioning of the service, ranging from bike malfunctioning to empty/full stations, helping the local government to improve and optimize the service. The reporting can be done via phone, website, email, a visit to the front office and, from 2017 onwards, also via a mobile application. In 2019, 19,647 users submitted service-related issues. In line with existing channel choice research (Madsen, Hofmann, & Pieterse, 2019; Madsen & Kræmmergaard, 2015), *SmartBike*'s user-reporters continue to favor traditional or previously implemented digital channels over the recently implemented new digital channel, although it is an innovative service per excellence. Among the users who reported service-related issues exclusively through one channel in 2019, the traditional channels stand out as being used the most (92.89%), followed by the m-government channel (5.88%), and the e-government channels (1.23%).

We argue that *SmartBike* is a compelling case to examine user-reporters' channel choice, as the sharing aspect implies the involvement of multiple stakeholders and the 'crowd', while the 'smartness' entails a reconfiguration of the interactions between the actors involved and their surrounding environment (Gil-Garcia et al., 2016; Ma, Lan, Thornton, Mangalagu, & Zhu, 2018; William, Webster, & Leleux, 2018). Especially, when examining city bike-sharing, this solution involves the innovative movement from private ownership of vehicles to 'usership'. It also implies a redefinition of the users' role, since they become both recipient and source of the services' information, and they bring in their resources to shared platforms (Docherty, Marsden, & Anable, 2018). Citizen reporting or citizen sourcing is, therefore, considered "the common unit" of smart services (Johnson, Robinson, & Philpot, 2020).

4.2. Sample and data collection

Data were collected from two distinct sources. First, we conducted an online survey among all users older than 16 who have a *SmartBike* yearly membership (approximately 60,000 users). The survey collected information on users' characteristics (i.e., gender, age, education level, occupational status), internet use, and satisfaction with the channel. A total of 13,449 users returned the questionnaire, reaching a response rate of approximately 22%. However, we limited our analysis to users who reported service-related issues exclusively via the traditional, e-government, or m-government channels between January 2019 till the end of October 2019 (when the survey was distributed). The population of analysis, therefore, consists of 3530 user-reporters. Second, we combined the survey data with *SmartBike* log data on user-reporters' membership length, frequency of service use, and actual reporting behavior via the traditional (phone and front office), e-government (website and email), and m-government (mobile application) channels. Social Media channels (i.e., Facebook) are not included in the current analysis because they are not yet fully operational as a *SmartBike*'s reporting channel. Survey responses were linked to actual behavior using anonymous user IDs.

Collecting data from multiple sources diminishes the risks of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003). As Petter, Delone, and Mclean

(2008) state, frequent reporters tend to self-report their behavior as too low, while occasional reporters tend to overestimate it. Therefore, relying on user-reporters' actual behavior, instead of their intention to use, substantially strengthens the validity and reliability of the conclusions (Petter et al., 2008; Podsakoff et al., 2003).

To examine the representativeness of our population of analysis, we compared respondents' actual reporting behavior, frequency of use of *SmartBike*, membership length, gender, age, occupational status, and language to the corresponding total population of *SmartBike* users. The population of analysis appears to be representative of all *SmartBike* users, except for professionally active users and females who are more represented in our population of analysis (see Appendix B and C).

4.3. Operationalization²

The variables were operationalized following previous channel choice studies (Ebbers, Jansen, Pieterse, & van de Wijngaert, 2016; Reddick et al., 2020; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014). The dependent variable is a categorical variable specifying users' actual channel choice behavior when reporting service-related issues (e.g., broken bikes, empty/full stations, vandalism) in 2019. The first category includes the users who exclusively reported service-related issues via traditional channels (front office and the phone), the second category consists of the users who exclusively reported service-related issues via e-government channels (website and emails), while the third category includes users who exclusively reported service-related issues via the m-government channel (mobile application).

The age categories were created following the quartiles of the distribution. Users' internet use was divided into three categories: low (less than 1 h a day), medium (between 1 and 3 h a day), and high (more than 3 h a day). This variable does not include respondents who do not use the internet daily, as this category did not contain enough observations. The occupational status was divided into two categories; professionally active and professionally inactive. The education levels were created following the distribution of our population and consist of three categories: low, medium, and high. Users' service experience is operationalized by membership length in months, and the frequency of service use which refers to the number of rides made in a year. Both users' service experience variables were derived from the log data. Users' satisfaction with the m-government channel was measured using a single item, on a scale from 1 (highly dissatisfied) to 5 (highly satisfied). Users do not solely use the mobile application to report service-related issues but also to plan their routes and to receive real-time information on bikes and bike stations.

4.4. Measures

4.4.1. Dependent variable: User-reporters' channel choice

In line with previous studies (e.g., Ebbers, Jansen, Pieterse, & van de Wijngaert, 2016; Teerling & Pieterse, 2011; P. Wu, 2012), and despite the implemented new technological advances, we observe that *SmartBike*'s user-reporters still prefer to report service-related issues via traditional channels. Among the user-reporters, 90.17% have reported service-related issues through the traditional channels, 1.44% through the e-government channels, and 8.39% through the m-government channel (see Table 1.).

4.4.2. Independent variables

Table 2. displays the descriptive statistics of the variables predicting user-reporters' channel choice. Concerning the digital divide variables, our population of analysis is characterized by middle-aged, highly educated, professionally active user-reporters who have a medium

² The detailed operationalization of the variables used in the model can be found in Appendix A.

Table 1
Dependent variable – Descriptive statistics.

Actual reporting behavior	Descriptive
Traditional channels (1, 2 & 3)	90.17%
(1) Exclusive Phone	89.69%
(2) Exclusive Office	0.14%
(3) Phone and Office	0.34%
E-government channels (4, 5 & 6)	1.44%
(4) Exclusive Email	0.51%
(5) Exclusive Website	0.91%
(6) Email and Website	0.03%
M-government channel	8.39%
Number of observations	3530

Table 2
Independent variables – Descriptive statistics.

Independent variables	Descriptive
Gender	
Female	48.05%
Male	51.95%
Age	
Mean	37.54
Standard deviation	12.37
Minimum	16
Maximum	82
Education	
Low education level	15.04%
Medium education level	2.69%
High education level	82.27%
Occupational status	
Professionally active	86.97%
Professionally inactive	13.03%
Use of the internet	
Low internet use	12.49%
Medium internet use	65.47%
High internet use	22.04%
Frequency of service use	
Mean	179.96
Standard deviation	155.97
Minimum	1
Maximum	1187
Membership length	
Mean	42.88
Standard deviation	30.54
Minimum	2
Maximum	102
Satisfaction with the mobile application	
Mean	3.41
Standard deviation	1.02
Minimum	1
Maximum	5
Number of observations	3530

internet use, and it is well-balanced between male and female respondents. Respondents are using *SmartBike* quite frequently, with an average of 180 rides per user in the last ten months (about one ride every two days). Moreover, user-reporters' average membership length with *SmartBike* is 43 months (approximately three years and a half). **Table 2.** also indicates that respondents appear to be satisfied with the m-government channel.

4.5. Multinomial logistic regression model

This study examines whether the digital divide determinants, user-reporters' experience with the service, and satisfaction with the m-government channel predict the probability that user-reporters will report service-related issues via the traditional or e-government channels compared to the m-government channel. Due to the nominal nature of the dependent variable, we estimate a multinomial logistic regression. This data analysis method is preferred over the estimation of a series of logistic regression as it "does not impose the constraints among the

coefficients that are implicit in the definition of the model" (Long & Freese, 2014, p. 174).

In multinomial logistic regression, one of the outcome categories of the dependent variable is set as the reference point. The model then compares individuals' probability of being part of the other categories to individuals' probability of being part of the reference point. In addition, Long and Freese (2014, p. 171) state that "the effects of the independent variables are allowed to differ for each outcome". For the analysis, we set the m-government channel as the reference category, and we thus predict the probability that users choose to report service-related issues via the traditional or e-government channels compared to the m-government channel given a set of predictors.

5. Empirical analysis

Table 3 presents the coefficients and the robust standard errors resulting from the multinomial logistic regression. As the model is nonlinear, the coefficients are not easily interpretable. Therefore, we transformed the coefficients into relative risk ratios by exponentiating them (Long & Freese, 2014). A relative risk ratio below one means that the predictor is negatively associated with user-reporters' choice of the channel compared to the reference category, holding the other factors

Table 3
User-reporters' channel choice – Multinomial Logistic Regression^a.

Variables	M-government channel			
	Traditional channels		E-government channels	
	Coefficient (SE)	RRR	Coefficient (SE)	RRR
<i>Gender</i>				
Male (ref. Female)	-0.331 (0.129)*	0.718	-0.796 (0.307)**	0.451
<i>Age (ref. 16–28)</i>				
29–34	-0.060 (0.164)	0.941	-0.559 (0.486)	0.572
35–47	0.326 (0.178) ⁺	1.385	0.066 (0.460)	1.068
Above 47	1.155 (0.238)***	3.174	1.313 (0.494)**	3.718
<i>Education level (ref. low)</i>				
Medium	0.420 (0.621)	1.521	1.073 (1.051)	2.925
High	-0.287 (0.195)	0.751	0.036 (0.474)	1.036
<i>Occupation (ref. professionally inactive)</i>				
Professionally active	-0.408 (0.206)*	0.665	0.027 (0.491)	1.028
<i>Internet use (ref. low)</i>				
Medium	-0.610 (0.287)*	0.544	-0.766 (0.562)	0.465
High	-0.684 (0.305)*	0.505	-0.188 (0.642)	0.828
Satisfaction mobile application	-0.530 (0.070)***	0.588	-0.332 (0.155)*	0.717
Membership length	0.021 (0.003)***	1.021	0.015 (0.006)*	1.015
Frequency of service use	0.001 (0.0004)**	1.001	-0.0007 (0.001)	0.999
Constant	4.466 (0.464)	-	-0.199 (1.002)	-
<i>N</i>	3530		3530	
Log-Likelihood	-1155.732		-1155.732	
Wald Chi-square	192.38***		192.38***	
Pseudo R ²	0.097		0.097	

^a Note: multinomial logistic regression with coefficients, robust standard errors into parentheses, and relative risk ratios (RRR).

⁺ $p < 0.1$.
* $p < 0.05$.
** $p < 0.01$.
*** $p < 0.001$.

constant. In contrast, a relative risk ratio above one means that the predictor is positively associated with user-reporters' choice of the channel compared to the reference category, *ceteris paribus*.

5.1. Empirical results

5.1.1. User-reporters' personal characteristics

The digital divide was found to be a relevant predictor of user-reporters' channel choice in the context of smart mobility coproduction. This finding is in line with previous channel choice studies (e.g., Ebberts, Jansen, Pieterse, & van de Wijngaert, 2016; Reddick et al., 2020; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014).

We find support for H1a as the results indicate that male users are less likely than female users to report service-related issues through the traditional and e-government channels compared to the m-government channel. As outlined in H1b, we find evidence that older users are more likely than younger users to report service-related issues via the traditional and e-government channels compared to the m-government channel. Moreover, we observe that, compared to professionally inactive users (H1c), professionally active users are less likely to report service-related issues through the traditional channel compared to the m-government channel. However, occupational status does not predict users' choice to report via the e-government channels over the m-government channel. Contrary to our expectations, education (H1d) does not appear to predict user-reporters' channel choice.

In this respect, our results show mixed support for H1e. Compared to users who do not use the internet often, users who have a medium or high internet use are less likely to report service-related issues via the traditional channels compared to the m-government channel. This finding does not only support our hypothesis and confirms previous studies (e.g., Reddick & Turner, 2012), but also highlights the relevance of examining the digital divide beyond access to the internet. Nevertheless, internet use does not appear to be a significant predictor of user-reporters' choice to use the e-government channels over the m-government channel.

5.1.2. User-reporters' service experience

We find contrasting results concerning user-reporters' experience (H2). First, users who have been using *SmartBike* for a longer period are more likely to report service-related issues via the earlier implemented traditional and e-government channels compared to the m-government channel. Similarly, users who use *SmartBike* more frequently, are more likely to report service-related issues through the traditional channels compared to the m-government channel. These results further supports the argument of SQB theory (Wang et al., 2013) and the empirical evidence from existing channel choice studies (e.g., Rey-Moreno et al., 2018; Teerling & Pieterse, 2011). Despite these findings, when examining user-reporters' channel choice between the m-government and e-government channels, users' frequency of service use is not a significant predictor.

5.1.3. User-reporters' satisfaction with the mobile application

In line with our assumption outlined in H3, the results indicate that users' satisfaction with the m-government channel is associated with users' channel choice. Similarly to previous research examining the relationship between satisfaction and channel choice (Devaraj et al., 2002; Montoya-Weiss et al., 2003), we observe that user-reporters who are more satisfied with the m-government channel are also more likely to report service-related issues via the m-government channel compared to the traditional and e-government channels.

5.2. Goodness of fit and post-estimation test

The Wald Chi-Square test (192.38 with $p < 0.000$) and the Pseudo R^2 (0.0965) indicate that the current model fits the data better than a model that would solely include the intercept. Following the empirical

Table 4

Wald test for combining alternatives.

Combinations tested	Chi-square	df	P > Chi-square
M-government channel versus Traditional channels	172.715	12	0.000
M-government channel versus E-government channels	45.322	12	0.000
Traditional channels versus E-government channels	21.041	12	0.050

analysis, this study performs a Wald test (see Table 4) to examine whether two outcomes of our dependent variable should be collapsed into one category (Long & Freese, 2014). Long and Freese (2014, p.184) highlight that "[i]f two outcomes are indistinguishable with respect to the variables in the model, then you can obtain more efficient estimates by combining them". The results of the Wald test indicate that the traditional channels, the e-government channels, and the m-government channel can be distinguished by the independent variables included in the model. More precisely, the results highlight that the outcomes can be distinguished by the predictors included in the model, indicating that merging some of the channels would not result in more efficient estimates.

6. Implications

6.1. Implications for research

Previous studies have primarily analyzed users' channel choice through users' intentions to use the channel (e.g., Ebberts, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Reddick et al., 2020; Reddick & Anthopoulos, 2014). Yet, past research shows that users tend to overestimate and/or underestimate their channel use (Petter et al., 2008). Since the present study examined users' actual reporting behavior, it advances the empirical evidence on channel choice while reducing potential common method bias, and increasing the validity and reliability of the results.

This study identified user-reporters' personal factors that are significantly associated to users' actual choice for the m-government channel over traditional and e-government channels. Our research demonstrated that membership length and frequency of service use are significantly associated with user-reporters' channel choice in a citizen sourcing setting. This finding highlights the relevance of user-reporters' service experience, which is related to the potential development of habits with prior implemented channels. Moreover, satisfactory experiences are also relevant in understanding users' channel choice. As argued by Limayem et al.'s (2007), satisfaction promotes the development of new habits that induce users' adoption of innovations. In line with this observation and existing channel choice studies (Ebberts, Jansen, & van Deursen, 2016; Reddick, 2017), our study shows that users' satisfaction with the mobile application is related to the actual choice of the respective channel, compared to traditional and e-government channels. In light of these observations, our findings contribute to channel choice theory and open up directions for future research to further examine the role of users' experiences and habits when choosing m-government channels in real-life settings.

6.2. Implications for practice

Our research provides relevant insights for practitioners on users' reporting behavior in a smart service context. Three main findings stand out. First, we observed that the digital divide determinants are significant predictors of user-reporters' channel choice. This finding implies that public service producers should pay attention to users' age and gender in order to configure effective and inclusive public services while acknowledging the limitations of implementing (new) digital channels to engage public service users.

Second, we find that users mostly report via traditional channels. A digital-by-default citizen sourcing strategy might, therefore, be problematic. Policy makers should take into consideration that public service users might prefer traditional channels as exclusive means to report service-related issues compared to (new) digital channels.

Third, the adoption of m-government channels is not automatic (Teerling & Pieterse, 2011; van Dijk et al., 2008). In this respect, the design and implementation of digital tools to engage users in reporting are important for the adoption of m-government channels, as evidenced by our findings on channel satisfaction. Aspects such as user-friendliness, ease of use, sense of enjoyment, and responsiveness might be particularly important when offering (new) digital channels to engage users in reporting efforts. Even more important, though, are users' habits. Service experience is associated with channel choice. Users' choice of m-government channel entails a learning process that starts with users' knowledge of the channels and their potential advantages. Therefore, the offer of new digital tools needs to be accompanied by policies for behavioral change in order to induce long-term users to make the switch. This implication is particularly important in the context of constrained resources, since receiving service reports through traditional channels is more resource-intensive than receiving them through digital channels (Teerling & Pieterse, 2011; P. Wu, 2012). Information campaigns, for instance, might improve users' knowledge of the availability and usefulness of the m-government channels available for reporting. Multi-channel strategies, such as the promotion of the use of m-government channels when users visit the front office, might constitute another strategy for policymakers when trying to increase users' voluntary reporting behavior.

6.3. Limitations and direction for future research

This study combined survey data with log data on actual reporting behavior and, in this way, expands current work on channel choice that has mainly relied on users' intentions. Still, this research only includes user-reporters who participated in the online survey, resulting in a potential under-coverage of individuals with limited internet access (Bethlehem, 2010). However, our population of analysis does not show an over-representation of user-reporters who exclusively use the m-government channel. Moreover, 86% of the Flemish population used the internet (almost) every day in 2019 (Statistiek Vlaanderen, 2020), reducing the potential limitations associated with online surveys. Our population of analysis is also very similar to the real population (see Appendix B and C).

Second, the focus on the reporting system of a smart bike-sharing service constrains the generalizability of our conclusion to this specific

service and nature of interaction. We believe that this finding can be applied to smart services in similar contexts. The framework and method used in this study enable future research to examine the phenomenon in different smart service settings, and of a broader range of e-government and m-government channels (e.g., social media, SMS, and WhatsApp).

Third, our study confirms a significant relationship between m-government channel satisfaction and channel choice. Yet, future research should further develop and confirm this initial finding by incorporating additional measures of channel satisfaction, including aspects such as channel attractiveness (see for instance Wirtz & Birkmeyer, 2018).

Finally, although our study provides insights on explanatory factors (i.e., the digital divide, service experience, and satisfaction with the m-government channel) for channel choice behavior, causal pathways cannot be identified. Our findings on users' service experience, related to the development of habits, should be explored further through longitudinal data.

7. Concluding remarks

User-reporters of a smart bike-sharing scheme appear to still prefer traditional channels over m-government channels when reporting service-related issues. This phenomenon is striking in light of the increasing adoption of ICT by the public sector, and the potential advantages that ICT offers to user-reporters and the government. Therefore, this study aimed to explain users' channel choice to report service-related issues, by examining the digital divide, users' service experience, and satisfaction with the m-government channel. Our findings demonstrate that the digital divide-related characteristics of user-reporters using m-government, e-government, and traditional channels do significantly differ. Moreover, this study confirms that membership length and frequency of use, related to users' habits and experience, as well as users' satisfaction with innovative channels, should be taken into consideration when analyzing (digital) channel choice behavior. While a digital-by-default strategy might be challenging, our findings provide practical insights for regular service producers that rely on multiple channels for citizen sourcing efforts.

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Appendix A. Operationalization

Variable names	Data source	Operationalization
<i>Dependent variable</i>		
Channel choice	Log data	0 = Exclusive use of the m-government channel (mobile application) 1 = Exclusive use of the traditional channels (phone and office) 2 = Exclusive use of the e-government channels (email and website)
<i>Independent variables</i>		
Gender	Survey	0 = Females 1 = Males
Age	Survey	0 = 16–28 years old 1 = 29–34 years old 2 = 35–47 years old 3 = Above 47 years old
Education	Survey	0 = Low education level (no diploma, primary education, and secondary education) 1 = Medium education level (post-secondary, non-tertiary education) 2 = High education level (bachelor or equivalent, master or equivalent, and doctorate)
Occupational status	Survey	

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(continued)

Variable names	Data source	Operationalization
		0 = Professionally inactive (never did any paid work, student, homemaker/housewife, retired, disable/incapacitated for work, and unemployed)
		1 = Professionally active (self-employed, employed, public servant)
Internet use	Survey	0 = Low internet use (less than 1 h a day) 1 = Medium internet use (between 1 and 3 h a day) 2 = High internet use (more than 3 h a day)
Satisfaction with the mobile application	Survey	1 = Highly dissatisfied to 5 = Highly satisfied
Membership length	Log data	2 to 102 (number of months)
Frequency of service use	Log data	1 to 1187 (number of rides)

Appendix B. Representativeness check – Dependent variable

Actual reporting behavior	Population	Sample
Traditional channels (1, 2 & 3)	92.89%	90.17%
(1) Exclusive Phone	92.35%	89.69%
(2) Exclusive Office	0.20%	0.14%
(3) Phone and Office	0.34%	0.34%
E-government channels (4, 5 & 6)	1.23%	1.44%
(4) Exclusive Email	0.55%	0.51%
(5) Exclusive Website	0.68%	0.91%
(6) Email and Website	0.01%	0.03%
M-government channel	5.88%	8.39%
Number of observations	16,086	3530

Appendix C. Representativeness check

Variables	Population	Sample
Frequency of service use		
Mean	174.60	179.96
Standard deviation	162.26	155.97
Minimum	1	1
Maximum	2413	1187
Membership length		
Mean	40.32	42.88
Standard deviation	29.31	30.54
Minimum	2	2
Maximum	102	102
Gender		
Female	43.52%	48.05%
Male	56.48%	51.95%
Age		
Mean	35.41	37.54
Standard deviation	11.90	12.37
Minimum	16	16
Maximum	86	82
Occupational status		
Professionally active	68.38%	86.97%
Professionally inactive	31.62%	13.03%
Language		
Dutch	92.09%	93.48%
English	7.91%	6.51%
Number of observations	16,086	3530

References

- Abu-Tayeh, G., Neumann, O., & Stuermer, M. (2018). Exploring the motives of citizen reporting engagement: Self-concern and other-orientation. *Business and Information Systems Engineering*, 60(3), 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-018-0530-8>.
- Bethlehem, J. (2010). Selection Bias in Web Surveys. *International Statistical Review*, 78, 161–188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-5823.2010.00112.x>.
- Cardullo, P., & Kitchin, R. (2018). Being a “citizen” in the smart city: up and down the scaffold of smart citizen participation in Dublin, Ireland. *GeoJournal*, (84), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-018-9845-8>.
- Carlson, J. R., & Zmud, R. W. (1999). Channel expansion theory and the experiential nature of media richness perceptions. *Academy of Management Journal*, 42(2), 153–170. <https://doi.org/10.2307/257090>.
- Clark, B. Y., & Brudney, J. L. (2019). Citizen representation in City government-driven crowdsourcing. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work*, 28, 883–910. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10606-018-9308-2>.
- van Deursen, A. J. A. M., & van Dijk, J. A. G. M. (2014). *The digital divide shifts to differences in usage*. 16(3) pp. 507–526. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444813487959>.
- van Deursen, A. J. A. M., & van Dijk, J. A. G. M. (2019). The first-level digital divide shifts from inequalities in physical access to inequalities in material access. *New Media & Society*, 21(2), 354–375. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818797082>.
- Devaraj, S., Fan, M., & Kohli, R. (2002). Antecedents of B2C channel satisfaction and preference: Validating e-commerce metrics. *Information Systems Research*, 13(3), 316–333. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.13.3.316.77>.
- van Dijk, J. A. G. M. (2020). *The digital divide*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- van Dijk, J. A. G. M., Peters, O., & Ebbens, W. E. (2008). Explaining the acceptance and use of government internet services: A multivariate analysis of 2006 survey data in the Netherlands. *Government Information Quarterly*, 25(3), 379–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2007.09.006>.
- Docherty, I., Marsden, G., & Anable, J. (2018). The governance of smart mobility. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 115, 114–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2017.09.012>.

- Draft, R. L., & Lengel, R. H. (1986). Organizational information requirements, media richness and structural design. *Management Science*, 32, 554–571.
- Ebberts, W. E., Jansen, M. G. M., Pieterson, W. J., & van de Wijngaert, L. A. L. (2016). Facts and feelings: The role of rational and irrational factors in citizens' channel choices. *Government Information Quarterly*, 33(3), 506–515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2016.06.001>.
- Ebberts, W. E., Jansen, M. G. M., & van Deursen, A. J. A. M. (2016). Impact of the digital divide on e-government: Expanding from channel choice to channel usage. *Government Information Quarterly*, 33(4), 685–692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2016.08.007>.
- Ebberts, W. E., Pieterson, W. J., & Noordman, H. N. (2008). Electronic government: Rethinking channel management strategies. *Government Information Quarterly*, 25(2), 181–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2006.11.003>.
- Ertiö, T.-P. (2018). Plan on the move: Mobile participation in planning (University of Turku). Retrieved from <http://www.utupub.fi/handle/10024/144328>.
- Ertiö, T.-P., Ruoppila, S., & Thiel, S. K. (2016). Motivations to use a mobile participation application. In E. Tambouris, P. Panagiotopoulos, Ø. Sæbo, & M. A. Wimmer (Eds.), *ePart 2016, LNCS 9821* (pp. 138–150). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45074-2_11.
- Fatehikia, M., Kashyap, R., & Weber, I. (2018). Using Facebook ad data to track the global digital gender gap. *World Development*, 107, 189–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.03.007>.
- Fugini, M., & Teimourikia, M. (2016). The role of ICT in co-production of e-government public services. In M. Fugini, E. Bracci, & M. Sicilia (Eds.), *Co-production in the public sector* (pp. 119–139). Cham: Springer.
- Gil-García, J. R., Zhang, J., & Puro-Cid, G. (2016). Conceptualizing smartness in government: An integrative and multi-dimensional view. *Government Information Quarterly*, 33(3), 524–534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2016.03.002>.
- Johnson, P. A., Robinson, P. J., & Philpot, S. (2020). Type, tweet, tap, and pass: How smart city technology is creating a transactional citizen. *Government Information Quarterly*, 37(1), 101414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2019.101414>.
- de Jong, M. D. T., Neulen, S., & Jansma, S. R. (2019). Citizens' intentions to participate in governmental co-creation initiatives: Comparing three co-creation configurations. *Government Information Quarterly*, 36(3), 490–500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2019.04.003>.
- Kopackova, H., & Libalova, P. (2019). Quality of citizen reporting tools at municipal level. *Journal of Information Systems Engineering & Management*, 4(3).
- Kubicek, H. (2016). What difference does the “E” make? Comparing communication channels in public consultation and collaboration processes. In , *19. Public administration and information technology* (pp. 307–331). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-25403-6_15.
- Lan, J., Ma, Y., Zhu, D., Mangalagiu, D., Thornton, T., Lan, J., ... Thornton, T. F. (2017). Enabling value co-creation in the sharing economy: The case of Mobike. *Sustainability*, 9(1504). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9091504>.
- Lember, V., Brandsen, T., & Tonurist, P. (2019). The potential impacts of digital technologies on co-production and co-creation. *Public Management Review*, 21(11), 1665–1686. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2019.1619807>.
- Limayem, M., Hirt, S. G., & Cheung, C. M. K. (2007). How habit limits the predictive power of intention: The case of information systems continuance. *MIS Quarterly*, 31(4), 705–737. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25148817>.
- Linders, D. (2012). From e-government to we-government: Defining a typology for citizen coproduction in the age of social media. *Government Information Quarterly*, 29(4), 446–454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2012.06.003>.
- Long, J. S., & Freese, J. (2014). *Regression models for categorical dependent variables using Stata* (3rd ed.). Stata Press.
- Ma, Y., Lan, J., Thornton, T., Mangalagiu, D., & Zhu, D. (2018). Challenges of collaborative governance in the sharing economy: The case of free-floating bike sharing in Shanghai. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 197, 356–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.06.213>.
- Madsen, C.Ø., & Hofmann, S. (2019). Multichannel management in the public sector: A literature review. *The Electronic Journal of E-Government*, 17(1), 20–35.
- Madsen, C.Ø., Hofmann, S., & Pieterson, W. (2019). Channel choice complications. In I. Lindgren, M. Janssen, H. Lee, A. Polini, M. P. R. Bolívar, H. J. Scholl, & E. Tambouris (Eds.), *EGOV 2019* (pp. 139–151). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27325-5_11.
- Madsen, C.Ø., & Kræmmergaard, P. (2015). Channel choice: A literature review. In , *9248. Lecture notes in computer science (Including subseries lecture notes in artificial intelligence and lecture notes in bioinformatics)* (pp. 3–18). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-22479-4_1.
- Michels, A. (2011). Innovations in democratic governance: How does citizen participation contribute to a better democracy? *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 77(2), 275–293. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852311399851>.
- Montoya-Weiss, M. M., Voss, G. B., & Grewal, D. (2003). Determinants of Online Channel use and overall satisfaction with a relational, multichannel service provider. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 31(4), 448–458. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070303254408>.
- Norris, P. (2001). *Digital divide : Civic engagement, information poverty, and the internet worldwide*. Cambridge, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Offenhuber, D. (2015). Infrastructure legibility—a comparative analysis of open311-based citizen feedback systems. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 8, 93–112. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjres/rsu001>.
- Ogunola, O. M., Rowley, J., & Johnson, F. (2017). The multi-dimensional digital divide: Perspectives from an e-government portal in Nigeria. *Government Information Quarterly*, 34(2), 329–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2017.02.002>.
- O'Reilly, T. (2010). Government as a platform. In *Open government: Collaboration, transparency, and participation in practice* (pp. 11–39). Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media.
- Petter, S., Delone, W., & Mclean, E. (2008). Measuring information systems success: Models, dimensions, measures, and interrelationships. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 17, 236–263. <https://doi.org/10.1057/ejis.2008.15>.
- Pieterson, W. (2009). *Citizen's channel behavior and public service channel strategy*.
- Pieterson, W., Teerling, M., & Ebberts, W. (2008). Channel perceptions and usage: Beyond media richness factors. In M. A. Wimmer, H. J. Scholl, & E. Ferro (Eds.), *5184. EGOV 2008, LNCS 5184* (pp. 219–230).
- Pieterson, W. J., & Ebberts, W. E. (2020). Channel choice evolution: An empirical analysis of shifting channel behavior across demographics and tasks. *Government Information Quarterly*, 37(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2020.101478>.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J.-Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in Behavioral research: A critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879–903. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.88.5.879>.
- Reddick, C. G. (2017). Determinants of citizens' mobile apps future use in Chinese local governments: An analysis of survey data. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 11(2), 213–235. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TG-11-2016-0078>.
- Reddick, C. G., Abdelsalam, H. M. E., & Elkadi, H. A. (2012). Channel choice and the digital divide in e-government: The case of Egypt. *Information Technology for Development*, 18(3), 226–246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2011.643206>.
- Reddick, C. G., & Anthopoulos, L. (2014). Interactions with e-government, new digital media and traditional channel choices: Citizen-initiated factors. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 8(3), 398–419. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TG-01-2014-0001>.
- Reddick, C. G., & Turner, M. (2012). Channel choice and public service delivery in Canada: Comparing e-government to traditional service delivery. *Government Information Quarterly*, 29(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2011.03.005>.
- Reddick, C. G., Zheng, Y., & Perlman, B. (2020). Channel choice in China: Correlates and determinates of satisfaction and use of government service channels in a survey of Chinese cities. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 14(1), 81–100. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TG-11-2019-0105>.
- Rey-Moreno, M., & Medina-Molina, C. (2017). Inhibitors of e-government adoption: Determinants of habit and adoption intentions. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 2(3), 172–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2017.01.001>.
- Rey-Moreno, M., Medina-Molina, C., & Barrera-Barrera, R. (2018). Multichannel strategies in public services: Levels of satisfaction and citizens' preferences. *International Review on Public and Nonprofit Marketing*, 15(1), 9–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12208-017-0188-9>.
- Rodríguez Müller, A. P., & Steen, T. (2019). Behind the Scenes of Coproduction of Smart Mobility: Evidence from a Public Values' Perspective. In I. Lindgren, et al. (Eds.), *Electronic Government. EGOV 2019. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 11685. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-30300-3>.
- Schmidhuber, L., Hilgers, D., Gegenhuber, T., & Etselstorfer, S. (2017a). The emergence of local open government: Determinants of citizen participation in online service reporting. *Government Information Quarterly*, 34(3), 457–469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2017.07.001>.
- Schmidhuber, L., Hilgers, D., Gegenhuber, T., & Etselstorfer, S. (2017b). The emergence of local open government: Determinants of citizen participation in online service reporting. *Government Information Quarterly*, 34(3), 457–469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2017.07.001>.
- Serra, L. C., Carvalho, L. P., Ferreira, L. P., Vaz, J. B. S., & Freire, A. P. (2015). Accessibility evaluation of E-government Mobile applications in Brazil. *Procedia Computer Science*, 67, 348–357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.09.279>.
- Teerling, M. L., & Pieterson, W. (2011). How to improve e-government use: An empirical examination of multichannel marketing instruments. *Information Polity*, 16(2), 171–187. <https://doi.org/10.3233/IP-2011-0213>.
- Thijssen, P., & Van Dooren, W. (2016). Going online. Does ICT enabled-participation engage the young in local governance? *Local Government Studies*, 42(5), 842–862. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03003930.2016.1189413>.
- Thorngate, W. (1976). Must we always think before we act? *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 2(1), 31–35. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014616727600200106>.
- van Dijk, J. A. G. M. (2013). A theory of the digital divide. In M. Ragnedda, & G. W. Muschert (Eds.), *The digital divide: the internet and social inequality in international perspective* (pp. 29–51). (Routledge advances in sociology; Vol. 73, No. 73). Routledge.
- Vlaanderen, S. (2020). Internetgebruik naar gebruiksfrequentie. April 30. Retrieved August 19, 2020, from <https://www.statistiekvlaanderen.be/nl/internetgebruik-naar-gebruiksfrequentie>.
- Wang, Q., Song, P., & Yang, X. (2013). Understanding the substitution effect between online and traditional channels: Evidence from product attributes perspective. *Electronic Markets*, 23(3), 227–239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-012-0114-2>.
- Wellman, B., & Berkowitz, S. D. (1988). *Structural analysis in the social sciences. 2*. Cambridge University Press: Social structures: A network approach.
- William, C., Webster, R., & Leleux, C. (2018). Smart governance: Opportunities for technologically-mediated citizen co-production. *Information Polity*, 23, 95–110. <https://doi.org/10.3233/IP-170065>.
- Wirtz, B. W., & Birkmeyer, S. (2018). Mobile government services: An empirical analysis of mobile government attractiveness. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 41(16), 1385–1395. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2017.1390583>.
- Wolf, L., Bick, M., & Kummer, T.-F. (2017). The influence of situation-dependent factors on Mobile shopping usage. In *Proceedings of the 50th Hawaii international conference*

- on system sciences (pp. 4169–4178). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/41664>.
- Wu, P. (2012). A mixed methods approach to technology acceptance research. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 13(3), 172–187. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1jais.00287>.
- Wu, W.-N. (2017). Citizen relationship management system users' contact channel choices: Digital approach or call approach? *Information*, 8(8), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info8010008>.
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